

The effectiveness of formalin from sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract in histopathologic tissue preparation as compared to commercially prepared formalin

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Abstract

This research was centered to compare the formaldehyde content of the sweet orange peel extract to commercially prepared 10% neutral buffered formalin. The chosen two (2) specimens were pig's heart and liver. As replacement to human tissue, the pig provides specimens closely resembling human tissue. In spite of these advantages in Formalin, the health and safety risks are of concern and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) emphasized it as Group-A carcinogen. Motivated by this, the researchers made this research to find safer alternatives. The sweet orange peel was grated off and merged with water. The extract was separated from the residual solids using a clean cloth then filtered using Whatman 42 filter paper. After, samples were kept in normal refrigerator for three (3) days at a temperature of 4°C. The pH of the diluted samples was kept between 6 and 6.5. 0.1 N potassium hydroxide (KOH) was used to adjust the pH. The researchers used t-test for the statistical treatment. Based on the result of this study, there is a significant difference in terms of the effectiveness of formalin from sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract in histopathologic tissue preparation as compared to commercially prepared formalin. It was also discovered that sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) is not an effective alternative histopathologic fixative; however, future researchers may perform other methods of extracting the formaldehyde content from the sweet orange peel aside from manual extraction.

Keywords: Formaldehyde; Carcinogen; pH; Alternative; KOH; Citrus sinensis; T-test; Pig's heart; Pig's liver; 10% neutral buffered formalin; Tissue.

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Introduction

To fix the tissues, a variety of fixation techniques and fixative types have been developed and tested over time. The first and most important step in preparing tissue for microscopic inspection is fixation. In preparing tissues for histopathology, it is an essential part. Fixation aims to maintain the tissues in a living-like state, prevent bacterial putrefaction and autolysis, and improve the tissue's refractive index. Fixation is a complicated process of chemical processes that differs for various chemical groups that are present in tissues. At present, formalin is the fixative of choice. Most physicians are familiar with formalin due to its strong smell, which has made it a well-established fixative for common surgical pathologies (Dhengar et al., 2016; Sabarinath et al., 2013).

By the name of Alexander M. Butlerov, a Russian chemist, formaldehyde was first identified in 1859. This chemical was later made by Ferdinand Blum in the 19th century while working on formaldehyde for disinfection. Formalin has become the fixative of choice within only a few years, and formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue smeared with Hematoxylin and Eosin Y (H & E) had become the "Gold Standard." It has been stated that there is no other histopathology method that uses as much relevant data so quickly and for such a minimal cost. Despite these benefits, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) highlighted it as a Group-A carcinogen due to the dangers to human health (Chittemsetti et al., 2018). This inspired the researchers to conduct their study in an effort to identify safer substitutes.

Citrus is the common term used for Genus, a flowering plant of rue family, Rutaceae. It falls under subfamily Aurantioideae and tribe Citreae. Citrus has an unknown precise origin, but researchers believe it comes from the south and southeast tropical and subtropical regions of the world (Moore, 2001; Sharma et al., 2004; Ladaniya, 2008; Singh et al., 2010). Citrus has a difficult taxonomy and systematic, and the actual number of native species is undetermined because the majority of recognized species are hybrids that are reproduced through cloning. There is evidence to support the origin of hybrids in some natural true breeding species (Federici et al., 1998 as cited in Dorji & Yapwattanaphun, 2011).

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is:

1. To determine if sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract have a significant properties.
2. To determine if sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract have potential as an alternative formalin in histopathologic tissue preparation.
3. To gain more knowledge about sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*).
4. To lessen the potential hazards of using formalin.

Statement of the Problem

In this study, the researchers will investigate the effectiveness of the formaldehyde content of the sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract in histopathologic tissue preparation as compared to commercially prepared formalin. The tissue sections were assessed for the following criteria:

1. Nuclear details;
2. Cytoplasmic morphology clear details; and
3. Staining quality under light microscope.

Upon achieving this goal, the researchers sought to answer the following: Is there a significant difference in the results between the positive control 10% neutral buffered formalin and the experimental control sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract using Hematoxylin and Eosin Y stain?

Hypothesis

Based on the statistic result of this study, there is a significant difference in terms of the effectiveness of formalin from sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extract in histopathologic tissue preparation as compared to commercially prepared formalin.

Methods and Procedure

Research Design

The site of sample collection was located at 855 Carmen Plasan Street, Binondo, Manila. The study is an experimental research design focusing on the extraction of formaldehyde from sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel as substitute fixative agent for 10% Buffered Neutral Formalin in Histopathology tissue preparation. It was performed to determine if Sweet orange peel extract can serve as an efficient agent to contribute to the formalin-free laboratory movement as the fruit peel was suspected of a formaldehyde content as part of its natural form.

Method of Collection

The fruit specimen of *Citrus sinensis* collected from 855 Carmen Plasan Street, Binondo, Manila, was submitted to Bureau of Plant Industry in Manila for species identification and analysis. The study requires the use of two fresh tissues, heart and liver from domesticated adult pig collected at Dasmariñas City Slaughter House. It was immediately submerged in the control and sweet orange extract.

Research Method

The researchers used Completely Randomized Design (CRD) in order to determine the efficacy of Sweet orange peel extract as substitute fixative agent for 10% Buffered Neutral Formalin in Hematoxylin and Eosin Y (H&E) staining. It is the simplest experimental sampling design, in terms of data analysis and convenience. With this sampling technique, subjects were randomly assigned to treatments for errors. The study used one cross-sectional tissue from the heart of a domestic pig.

Research Experimentation

Peel Extraction

A. Equipment, Disposable, Reagents/Consumable

1 ½ box of sweet orange, stirring rod, gauze, distilled water, graduated cylinder, pipette, beaker

B. Procedure

Sweet orange peels were grated off and merged with water in 1:10 ratio. The extract was separated through Whatman 42 filter paper after being removed from the remaining particles using a clean cloth as a sieve. The extract was filtered multiple times to remove the residues. Samples were then stored for three (3) days at 4°C in a standard refrigerator. The diluted samples' pH was maintained between 6 and 6.5. 0.1 N Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) was used to adjust the pH (Nowshad et al., 2018).

C. Results

A total of 1000 ml per beaker of sweet orange peel extract is to be yielded, weighing 712 grams. A total of 1600 ml of sweet orange peel extract was collected and a total of 250 ml of potassium hydroxide was added. Both sweet orange peel extract and 10% neutral buffered formalin has a total of 1850 ml in each jar.

Buffer

The buffer used was Potassium Hydroxide (KOH). This substance is a stabilizer, thickening agent, and pH regulator in food. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has determined that it is generally safe for use as a direct human food ingredient based on the observance of various good manufacturing practice conditions of use.

Formalin Determination

Formaldehyde was found in sample solutions using Schiff's Reagent as an indicator. If there is a positive reaction, the color will turn in a bright-purplish-red.

Tissue Processing Procedure for Control and Experimental Groups

A. Equipment, Disposable, Reagents / Consumable

Cutting plate, Tissue cassette, 10% Formalin, Dehydrating agent, Beakers, Flask, Funnel, 95% ethanol, Paraffin wax, Xylene, Tap water, Hematoxylin, 1% Acid Alcohol, Ammonia Water, Eosin Y, Micro-mount, Microtome, Scalpel, Water bath, Tissue processor, Ammonia, Pen, Micropore, Glass slides, Cover slip, Microscope, Oven, Tray, Slide holder, Distilled water, 0.1N Potassium hydroxide, Leica Tissue Processor 1020

B. Procedure

The two selected tissues from domesticated pig were cut fresh into 3-5 mm slices through the cutting plate. A portion is to be selected for tissue examination and be place in a tissue cassette.

- a. **Tissue fixation:** The three sets of tissues in the tissue cassette were soak in 10% buffered formalin for 24 hours at room temperature.
- b. **Loafing:** The researchers slice or loaf the specimen for a better fixation after 24 hours.

- c. **Dehydration of tissue:** Using Leica Tissue Processor machine, the specimen will be soaked at each dehydrating agent at room temperature for six (6) hours. The beakers were labeled with increasing concentration of alcohol. The first three container would be 95% alcohol and the specimen will be soaked in one (1) hour per container. The last three container were 100% alcohol, and the specimen will be soaked for one (1) hour per container again.
- d. **Clearing:** The tissue is made translucent by reagent Xylene. It effectively takes out the dehydrating agent and replaces it with a fluid that is soluble in both the embedding medium and the dehydrating agent.
- e. **Infiltration:** Infiltration by setting the tissue for one (1) hour for each beaker containing paraffin wax for two (2) degrees above the melting point of paraffin which is 45°C to 68°C.
- f. **Sectioning with microtome:** The tissues were sliced into parts that could be placed on a slide once they had been attached. A microtome was used to complete this. The microtome is merely a knife with a mechanism for sliding a paraffin block across it at predetermined intervals (Anil & Rajendran, 2012).
- g. **Hematoxylin and Eosin Staining:** the procedures were followed:
 1. Soak to Xylene for five (5) minutes
 2. Soak to Xylene for another five (5) minutes
 3. Dip in 95% Ethyl alcohol for 10 times
 4. Dip in running water for five (5) times
 5. Soak it to Hematoxylin for 20 minutes
 6. Dip in running water or 10 times
 7. Dip in Acid alcohol for one (1) time
 8. Dip in running water for 10 times
 9. Dip in Ammonia for two (2) times
 10. Dip in running water for five (5) times
 11. Dip in Eosin Y for 10 times
 12. Dip in 95% Ethyl alcohol for 10 times
 13. Dip in 95% Ethyl alcohol for another 10 times
 14. Soak to Xylene for two (2) minutes
 15. Soak to Xylene for another two (2) minutes
 16. Air dry
 17. Labelling
 18. Mount and cover slip

Figure 1. Procedure

C. Expected Results

Tissue slides prepared using peel extract from sweet orange compared to that of tissue slides prepared using 10% Buffered Neutral Formalin as fixative agent. Tissue slides will give a good fixation result. The expected result would be: the tissue will adhere to the slide and will give a good appearance when viewed under microscope. The evaluation of specimen and the consultation of the rate of the efficacy of the peel extract as fixative agent will be done by two Registered Pathologists.

Data Collection

The processed slides would be assessed by two licensed Pathologists. There would be survey questionnaires containing different criteria to be evaluated and scored. The data from those evaluations would be used in this study. Data gathered from these questionnaires would determine the comparison of the *Citrus sinensis* (Sweet orange) peel extract and 10% Buffered Neutral Formalin as fixative agent.

Method of Evaluation

Two pathologists assessed the tissue slides through a blind evaluation. Each pathologists examined 12 slides (1-6 control, 7-12 sweet orange extract). A study made by Speilberg et al. (1993) was conducted evaluating the H&E slides by three (3) different examiners. The variables observed and the principal criteria for their evaluation were as follows:

1. Morphological appearance of nuclei:

- 1 - Damaged to no visible nuclei.
- 2 - Nuclei is roughly uneven with poor distribution of chromatin.
- 3 - Smooth and slightly oval nuclei with even distribution of chromatin.
- 4 - Smooth and round oval nuclei, with even distribution of chromatin.

2. Morphological appearance of cytoplasm:

- 1 - No cytoplasm outline with severe tears and holes and severely shrunken.
- 2 - Poorly outlined cytoplasm with mechanical artifacts and shrunken cytoplasm.
- 3 - Outlined cytoplasm, presence of small holes and tears, with slight shrinkage.
- 4 - Well outlined cytoplasm with intact components and no visible shrinkage.

3. Staining quality:

- 1 - The tissue has little to no color.
- 2 - The tissue specimen shows slight tinge of color.
- 3 - The tissue specimen is slightly pale.
- 4 - There is a high affinity of the dyes for tissue elements.

4. General Judgement

- 1 - Tissue did not stain and possessed shrunken un-outlined cytoplasm with tears and holes. An overall bad fixative.
- 2 - Shows slightly poor staining result. The cytoplasm is shrunken and contains mechanical artifacts. An overall poor fixative.
- 3 - Nuclei and cell morphology specimen shows slight errors. An overall good fixative.
- 4 - The tissue components are well intact and are easily recognizable, no presence of mechanical artifacts. It is well stained. An excellent fixative.

Statistical Treatment

The study was experimental and prone to random error. Hence, the study used the student's t-test and standard deviation as statistical treatment to observe the random error omitted from the experiment. To determine if the tested treatment is significant or not significant, conclusions were drawn using the p-value with the following as bases of interpretation:

p-value \leq 0.001 = significant

p-value \geq 0.001 = not significant

Rejection rule: Reject H_0 if p-value is less than α

Data collected from the assessments would be subjected to student's T-test where it would be treated and analyzed whether the data was significant at $P < .10$.

Results and Discussion

After the tissues were processed using 10% Neutral Buffered Formalin (slides 1-6) and sweet orange extract (slides 7-12), the organs were then evaluated by two selected pathologists based on different criteria.

Table 1. Reference scale for morphological appearance of nucleus

Arbitrary Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Interpretation
3.50-4.00	4	Smooth nuclei with even distribution.
2.50-3.49	3	Irregularly shaped with even distribution.
1.50-2.49	2	Nuclei is poorly preserved with uneven distribution.
1.00-1.49	1	No visible nuclei.

The table above shows the reference scale for Morphological Appearance of Nucleus. If a mean score falls within the range of 3.50-4.00 is verbally interpreted as *Smooth nuclei with even distribution*. If a mean score falls within the range of 2.50-3.49 is verbally interpreted as *Irregularly shaped with even distribution*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.50-2.49 is verbally interpreted as *Nuclei is poorly preserved with uneven distribution*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.00-1.49 is verbally interpreted as *No visible nuclei*.

Table 2. Reference scale for morphological appearance of cytoplasm

Arbitrary Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Interpretation
3.50-4.00	4	Well outlined cytoplasm with intact components and no visible.
2.50-3.49	3	Outlined cytoplasm. Few artifacts present. Slight shrinkage.
1.50-2.49	2	Poor outline of cytoplasm. Holes and tears are seen. Tissue is shrunken.
1.00-1.49	1	Tears and holes are present. Tissue is shrunken.

The table above shows the reference scale for Morphological Appearance of Cytoplasm. If a mean score falls within the range of 3.50-4.00 is verbally interpreted as *Well outlined cytoplasm with intact components and no visible*. If a mean score falls within the range of 2.50-3.49 is verbally interpreted as *Outlined cytoplasm; Few artifacts present; Slight shrinkage*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.50-2.49 is verbally interpreted as *Poor outline of cytoplasm; Holes and tears are seen; Tissue is shrunken*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.00-1.49 is verbally interpreted as *Tears and holes are present; Tissue is shrunken*.

Table 3. Reference scale for staining quality

Arbitrary Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Interpretation
3.50-4.00	4	Tissue is well stained. Has high dye affinity.
2.50-3.49	3	Tissue specimen is pale.
1.50-2.49	2	Tissue specimen has slight tinge of color.
1.00-1.49	1	Tissue has no color.

The table above shows the reference scale for Staining Quality. If a mean score falls within the range of 3.50-4.00 is verbally interpreted as *Tissue is well stained; Has high dye affinity*. If a mean score falls within the range of 2.50-3.49 is verbally interpreted as *Tissue specimen is pale*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.50-2.49 is verbally interpreted as *Tissue specimen has slight tinge of color*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.00-1.49 is verbally interpreted as *Tissue has no color*.

Table 4. Reference scale for general adjustment

Arbitrary Scale	Rating Scale	Verbal Interpretation
3.50-4.00	4	Tissue components are well intact and easily recognizable, well stained, and an excellent fixative.
2.50-3.49	3	Nuclei and cell morphology show slight errors. An overall good fixative.
1.50-2.49	2	Poor stain affinity. Exhibited tissue distortion. A poor fixative.
1.00-1.49	1	Tissue did not stain. Exhibited shrinkage with tears and holes. No visible nuclei. An overall bad fixative.

The table above shows the reference scale for General Adjustment. If a mean score falls within the range of 3.50-4.00 is verbally interpreted as *Tissue components are well intact and easily recognizable, well stained, and an excellent fixative*. If a mean score falls within the range of 2.50-3.49 is verbally interpreted *Nuclei and cell morphology show slight errors and an overall good fixative*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.50-2.49 is verbally interpreted as *Poor stain affinity, exhibited tissue distortion and a poor fixative*. If a mean score falls within the range of 1.00-1.49 is verbally interpreted as *Tissue did not stain, exhibited shrinkage with tears and holes, no visible nuclei and an overall bad fixative*.

Table 5. Mean score per criteria

Extract	Criteria	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Synthetic	Morphological Appearance of Nucleus	3.42	Irregularly shaped with even distribution.
	Morphological Appearance of Cytoplasm	3.08	Outlined cytoplasm. Few artifacts present. Slight shrinkage.
	Staining Quality	3.67	Tissue is well stained. Has High dye affinity.
	General Adjustment	3.58	Tissue components are well intact and easily recognizable. Well stained. An excellent fixative.
Orange Peel	Morphological Appearance of Nucleus	3.00	Irregularly shaped with even distribution.
	Morphological Appearance of Cytoplasm	2.92	Outlined cytoplasm. Few artifacts present. Slight shrinkage.
	Staining Quality	3.33	Tissue specimen is pale.
	General Adjustment	2.75	Nuclei and cell morphology show slight errors. An overall good fixative.

The table above shows that mean score per criteria of synthetic and orange peel. For morphological appearance of nucleus, both synthetic and orange obtained a mean score that is verbally interpreted as irregularly shaped with even distribution.

For morphological appearance of cytoplasm, both synthetic and orange obtained a mean score that is verbally interpreted as Outlined cytoplasm, few artifacts present, and slight shrinkage.

For Staining Quality, synthetic obtained a mean score that is verbally interpreted as Tissue is well stained and has high dye affinity; while orange peel obtained a mean score that is verbally interpreted as Tissue specimen is pale.

For General Adjustment, synthetic obtained a means core that is verbally interpreted as Tissue components are well-intact and easily recognizable, well-stained, and an excellent fixative; while orange peel obtained a means core that is verbally interpreted as Nuclei and cell morphology show slight errors and an overall good fixative.

Table 6. Test for significant difference

Criteria	P-value	Significance	H ₀ Decision
Morphological Appearance of Nucleus	0.197	Not Significant	Accept
Morphological Appearance of Cytoplasm	0.655	Not Significant	Accept
Staining Quality	0.111	Not Significant	Accept
General Adjustment	0.017	Significant	Reject

The table above shows the test for significant difference between synthetic and orange peel. For Morphological Appearance of Nucleus, the computed p-value is 0.197 which is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is no significant difference and null hypothesis is accepted. This would mean that in terms Morphological Appearance of Nucleus criteria, synthetic and orange peel resulted at the same level which is irregularly shaped with even distribution.

For Morphological Appearance of Cytoplasm, the computed p-value is 0.655 which is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is no significant difference and null hypothesis is accepted. This would mean that in terms Morphological Appearance of Cytoplasm criteria, synthetic and orange peel resulted at the same level which is Well outlined cytoplasm with intact components and no visible.

For Staining Quality, the computed p-value is 0.111 which is greater than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is no significant difference and null hypothesis is accepted. This would mean that in terms Staining Quality criteria, synthetic and orange peel resulted at the same level which is well outlined cytoplasm with tissue specimen is pale.

For General Adjustment, the computed p-value is 0.017 which is lower than .05 alpha level. Hence, there is significant difference and null hypothesis is rejected. This would mean that synthetic is significantly higher in general adjustment than orange peel.

Conclusions

With the results obtained during the experimentation, the researchers came up with the following conclusions. The specific problems within this study were answered:

1. Sweet orange peel extract (*Citrus sinensis*) cannot be used to replace 10% Neutral Buffered Formalin. While cutting the specimen it barely forms a ribbon unlike using the synthetic formalin it is easy to produce a ribbon like in cutting.
2. There is a significant difference between the synthetic and the sweet orange peel extract.
3. The Potassium Hydroxide is safe to be used in food to adjust pH and has been considered as generally safe as a direct human food ingredient by the FDA.
4. 10% Formalin is highly recommended as a fixative agent.

Recommendations

The researchers would like to advice to perform other method of extracting the formaldehyde content from the sweet orange peel aside from manual extraction. They can use machines or other devices for them to be able to collect more concentrated extract from it. Aside from these, the future researchers could also take time to observe the amount of time the stain on the tissue slides processed with sweet orange would last.

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